

STUDIES IN CELLULOSE ACETATE. PART II.

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During the preparation of cellulose acetates, an acetate having a theoretical acetic acid content of 62.5% corresponding to tri-acetate is produced at the early stage; but with the progress of reaction, this acetate passes through several intermediate stages yielding products soluble both in chloroform and in acetone and finally di-acetate is formed having acetic acid content of 48.8%. Hydrolysis of tri-acetate to di-acetate has been effected without the presence of acetic acid or water.

Cellulose tri-acetate contains 44.8% acetyl or 62.5% acetic acid content, the di-acetate, 35.0% acetyl or 48.8% acetic acid content and the mono-acetate, 21.1% acetyl or 29.4% acetic acid content.

That the tri-acetate with 62.5% acetic acid content is a definite chemical compound has been established (Hess, "Die Cellulose", 1928; Hess and Ljubitsch. *Ber.*, 1928, **61**, 1460; Barnett, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1921, **40**, 8; Ost, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1919, **32**, 66). Hess, Schultz and Messmer (*Annalen*, 1925, **444**, 266) have shown that cellulose tri-acetate, soluble in chloroform, can be prepared in crystal form and is the normal acetylation product of chemically unchanged cellulose. This view has been confirmed by X-ray analysts.

Tri-acetate is soluble in chloroform but the film, made out of it, is weak and brittle (*cf.* Ost, *loc. cit.*). Hence for technical purposes, tri-acetate is useless.

Miles (B. P. 19330, 1905) by the partial hydrolysis of the tri-acetate with 50% acetic acid obtained an acetone-soluble di-acetate. Dreyfus (F. P. 478 023, 1914; B. P. 312-098, 311-790, 308-322; U. S. P. 1,711 111) too, prepared the di-acetates from tri-acetates by hydrolysis using water alone. Di-acetates give much clearer and tougher films. Di-acetates prepared by Miles' process give acetic acid content varying between 51 and 58%. Di-acetates are generally soluble in acetone but insoluble in chloroform.

Ost (*loc. cit.*) has investigated the solubility of cellulose acetate in various solvents and found the acetic acid content of the cellulose acetate to be the guiding factor in its solubility in different solvents. The cause for the dissolution of the secondary or di-acetates in acetone and the property of dispersion of the resultant product in acetone have been ascribed to the amount of acetic acid and water present during the degradation of primary acetate to secondary acetate.

Yarsley ("Über die Herstellung und physikalischen Eigenschaften der Cellulose Acetate") corroborated the views of Ost and showed definitely that contrary

to the observations of Miles, Dreyfus and others, primary or tri-acetates, prepared by him, were soluble both in acetone and in chloroform. But the most satisfactory secondary or di-acetates were obtained from those tri-acetates which were difficultly soluble in acetone. Di-acetates prepared by him gave 53% acetic acid content.

According to Marsh and Wood ("An Introduction to the Chemistry of Cellulose", 1945, p. 327) solubility in chloroform is almost entirely determined by the extent of acetylation and increases rapidly where more than two-thirds of the available hydroxyl groups are acetylated. The solubility of cellulose acetate in acetone depends on the type of cellulose as well as on the extent of esterification, but it is not possible to produce an acetate which is completely soluble in acetone merely by interrupting the esterification at any stage.

Deripasko (*Cellulose Chem.*, 1931, 12, 254) has found that only acetates with acetic acid contents between 60 and 49% are soluble in acetone. A series of acetates with acetic acid contents varying from 60 to 57.5% was prepared and only acetates containing 57.4 to 57.8% were found soluble in ethyl acetate. Acetates containing 57% acetic acid were often found to be soluble both in chloroform and acetone.

From the above discussions it appears that the term "di-acetate" has been used in a very loose sense, as the lowest acetic acid content obtained, does not, as a rule, go below 51% (Miles' process) and goes as high as 58%, while theoretically di-acetate should contain as low as 48.8% of acetic acid content. Yarsley obtained 53%, whilst Hess *et al.* after repeated fractionation of acetone soluble secondary acetate narrowed down the acetic acid content to 51-53% but not to 48.8% as required theoretically. Barnett (*loc. cit.*) obtained a di-acetate having 48.8% of acetic acid content, but this acetate was mentioned as a fine white powder, soluble both in acetone and in chloroform, whilst according to other workers, di-acetate should be a white, fibrous mass, having its solubility only in acetone.

The absence of convincing data on this score, substantiated by their own experimental results, led the X-ray analysts to believe the acetone-soluble di-acetates to be a mixture of tri-acetate with varying proportions of unchanged cellulose, although this belief was hotly contested by workers in this line.

It appears from the works of the investigators, mentioned above, that they have overlooked the formation of a series of intermediate products, soluble both in chloroform and in acetone, in between the chloroform-soluble tri-acetate and acetone-soluble di-acetate which invariably occur during the process of the formation of cellulose acetates. The influence of the acetyl content or % acetic acid content was carefully examined by Coltof (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1937, 56, 363). The conditions of preparation were varied to obtain a series of secondary acetates with decreasing acetyl content. These amount to 62.5% for the tri-acetate and 48.8% for the di-acetate calculated on the basis of % weight of acetic acid.

TABLE I
Cellulose acetate.

Acetic acid content.	Solubility at room temp. in			Acetic acid content.	Solubility at room temp. in		
	CHCl ₃ .	acetone.	ethyl acetate.		CHCl ₃ .	acetone.	ethyl acetate.
60.0%	5	0	0	55.5%	4	5	4
58.9	5	2	—	54.5	3-4	5	—
58.5	5	3	—	51.0	3-4	5	3
57.2	5	4	2	52.8	3	5	2
56.8	5	5	—	48.0	0	2	—
50.0	5	5	—				

* The fig. 5 denotes complete dissolution, the fig. zero, complete insolubility.

It is evident that the relation between the dispersing and swelling action must increase with decreasing acetyl content.

The present author in a series of investigations has noted that in the preparation of cellulose acetates, during the first stage of acetylation, an acetate, soluble only in chloroform, is produced, which has an acetic acid content near about 62.5% as theoretically required for primary or tri-acetate. This acetate during the process of further reaction passes through several intermediate stages, where intermediate products are formed, which are soluble both in chloroform and in acetone to a varying degree till it reaches a stage where an acetate, soluble only in acetone and having acetic acid content of 48.8% (approx.) as theoretically required for di-acetate, is produced. If reaction is carried still further, the resultant acetate becomes progressively insoluble in acetone, acetic acid content having gone down below 48.8% (Tables II, III and IV).

The above course of reaction has been found to be a common feature in all the experiments undertaken under a given condition of a certain proportion of cellulose and acetylating mixture and temperature, but independent of the % catalyst (H₂SO₄ of *d* 1.84). Contrary to previous observations, it has been observed that the increase of H₂SO₄ up to 20.2% as a catalyst has no adverse effect on acetylation so far as the acetyl content of the product is concerned (Tables II-IV).

It has also been found that the hydrolysis of primary acetates (tri-) into secondary (di-) acetates can be brought about even without the presence of dilute acetic acid or water. The only difference observed between the one hydrolysed in the usual way and the other unhydrolysed, is longer hours required by the latter to give the same product or products. Besides this, no basic difference in the composition of the products or their solubility in different solvents has been observed (Table IV).

In the tables various degrees of solubility have been denoted by the following :

I. S. = insoluble ; P. S. = partly soluble ; M. S. = moderately soluble ; R. S. = readily soluble ; S = soluble ; C. S. = completely soluble ; A. S. = apparently soluble ; L. S. = less soluble ; P = plastic.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the experiments were conducted under the following conditions :

(i). The proportion of cellulose and acetylating mixture was kept as C : Ac : An = 1 : 5 : 4, where C = cellulose, Ac = glacial acetic acid, An = acetic anhydride.

(ii). Temperature was kept the same viz., at 25° for the first hour, at 30° for the second hour, at 35° for the third, 40° for the fourth, at 40-45° for the fifth and 45° for the 6th and all subsequent hours, till it was kept for overnight. After that the temperature was further raised to 50° during the period of hydrolysis and kept there at that temperature until it was kept again for overnight.

(iii). Period of reaction was maintained the same as far as possible in order to ensure uniform result (see the tables).

(iv). Percentage of catalyst (H_2SO_4 , *d* 1.84) used was varied within wide limits (from 11.0 to 20.2) but excepting a variation observed in the viscosity of the solution (solution was more viscous where less percentage of H_2SO_4 was used), no basic difference in the chemical composition of the resultant acetate has been found out (Tables II-IV).

TABLE II

No. of expt.	No. of sample.	H_2SO_4 (catalyst),	Duration of reaction (total hrs.)	Solubility at room temp. in		Acetic acid content.
				chloroform.	acetone.	
3.	1	14.7%	6	M, S.	I. S.	62.4%.
	2	—	8	S.	..	62.4
4.	1	16.6	6	M.S.	I.S.	62.4
	2	—	6	S.	..	62.4
5.	1	15.4	4	M S.	I.S.	62.4
	2	—	6	S.	..	62.4
	3	—	6	R.S.	Swelling & P.S.	61.2
6.	1	20.2	6	S.	I.S.	62.4
	2	—	8	R.S.	Swelling & P.S.	61.2

TABLE III

No. of expt.	No. of sample.	H ₂ SO ₄ (catalyst).	Duration of reaction (total hrs.).	*Period of hydrolysis (total hrs.).	Solubility at room temp. in		Acetic acid content.
					chloroform.	acetone.	
1.	1	11.0%	27.0	3.5	S.	C.S.	55.2%
2.	1	12.9	28.5	2.0	C.S.	"	56.4
	2	—	46.0	15.4	I.S.	"	50.4
3.	1	14.7	23.5	Nil	C.S.	A.S.	60.0
	2	—	25.0	1.0	"	S. but not readily	58.9
	3	—	26.0	2.0	"	R.S.	57.6
	4	—	26.5	2.5	"	"	57.6
	5	—	28.0	4.0	L.S.	"	55.2
	6	—	30.5	6.5	P.	C.S.	54.0
	7	—	31.0	7.0	"	"	54.0
	8	—	47.0	23.0	I.S.	"	49.2
	9	—	48.0	24.0	"	P.S.	49.0
	10	—	54.5	30.5	"	P.	47.4
	11	—	71.0	47.0	"	I.S.	45.6
	12	—	72.0	48.0	"	"	43.2
4.	1	16.6	25	Nil	C.S.	A.S.	61.2
	2	—	27	1.0	"	S.	59.9
5.	1	16.4	24.0	Nil	"	A.S.	61.2
	2	—	26.0	1.5	"	S.	57.6
	3	—	28.0	3.5	L.S.	C.S.	55.2
	4	—	32.0	7.5	P.	"	54.0
	5	—	48.0	23.5	I.	"	50.4
	6	—	59.0	28.5	"	"	49.2
6.	1	20.2	24.0	Nil	C.S.	S.	58.99
	2	—	26.0	1.5	L.S.	C.S.	57.6
	3	—	28.0	3.5	P.	"	54.0
	4	—	30.0	5.5	I.S.	"	52.8
	5	—	32.0	7.5	"	"	52.4
	6	—	48.0	23.5	"	P.	48.9
	7	—	55.0	30.5	"	I-S.	44.4

* After the addition of 65% acetic acid.

In all the experiments, Indian cotton having α -cellulose content of 99.5% was used. For the determination of acetic acid content the saponification method of Hess was followed ("Chemie der Cellulose", p. 415).

TABLE IV

No. of expt.	No. of sample.	H ₂ SO ₄ (catalyst).	Duration of reaction (total hrs.)	*Period of hydrolysis (total hrs.)	Solubility at room temp. in		Acetic acid.
					CHCl ₃ .	acetone.	
3.	1	14.7%	23.5	Nil	C.S.	A.S.	60.0%
	2	—	47.0	23.5	P.	C.S.	64.0
	3	—	72.0	48.5	I.S.	P.S.	48.0
4.	1	16.8	27	Nil	C.S.	S. not readily	58.8
	2	—	48	21.0	..	C.S.	55.0
	3	—	52	25.0	P.	..	52.8
	4	—	55	28.0	I.S.	..	51.8
	5	—	96	69.0	..	I.R.	44.4
	6	—	102	75.0	..	..	43.2
5.	1	18.4%	24	Nil	C.S.	A.S.	61.2
	2	—	26	2.0	..	S. but not readily	58.8
	3	—	28	4.0	..	..	58.8
	4	—	32	8.0	..	R.R.	57.8
	5	—	48	24.0	P.	C.S.	52.8
	6	—	58	29.0	I.S.	..	51.8
6.	1	20.2	24.0	Nil	C.S.	S.	58.8
	2	—	28.0	4.0	L.S.	C.S.	56.4
	3	—	32.0	8.0	I.S.	..	52.8
	4	—	48.0	24.0	..	..	50.4
	5	—	55.0	31.0	..	..	48.8

* Without the addition of dil. acetic acid or water.

Procedure.

Cellulose in the form of bleached cotton (50 g.) was added gradually to the acetylating mixture consisting of glacial acetic acid (250 c. c.), acetic anhydride (200 c. c.), H₂SO₄ (3.5 to 5.5 c. c.) previously cooled to about 20° taking care that the temperature did not rise above 25° (by cooling). After some time, the mass became pasty when the temperature was raised to 30° and kept at 30-35° till the mass became viscous. After some time temperature was raised to 45° and kept there till it became less viscous and transparent.

After 8 hours (the required reaction period) a test precipitate, washed to neutrality and dried, showed complete solubility in chloroform but complete insolubility in acetone (primary or tri-acetate). At this stage, it was kept overnight at room temperature. Next morning (about 24 hours) a test precipitate, washed to neutrality and dried, was found to be completely soluble in chloroform and apparently soluble in acetone. At this stage, the solution was hydrolysed with 65% acetic acid at 45-50°. After the hydrolysis had proceeded for a sufficient length of time the test precipitate was found completely soluble both in chloroform and in (25-28

hours). Next a stage was reached when the precipitate became soluble only in acetone and not in chloroform (about 48 hours), when the acetic acid content of the acetate was near about 48.8% (theoretically required by di-acetate ; sample 2 in Expt. No. 2, samples 8 and 9 in Expt. No. 3, samples 5 and 6 in Expt. No. 5 in Table III and sample 3 in Expt. No. 3, sample 4 in Expt. No. 4, sample 6 in Expt. No. 5, and samples 4 and 5 in Expt. No. 6, in Table IV).

When hydrolysis was carried out still further beyond 48.8%, the acetate showed progressive insolubility even in acetone and a stage was reached when it became completely insoluble (samples 10, 11, and 12 in Expt. No. 3, samples 6 and 7 in Expt. 6. Table III, samples 5 and 6 in Expt. No. 4, Table IV).

DISCUSSION

A perusal of the various important methods of acetylation, adopted by Miles, Dreyfus, Yarsley and others will show that these authors have used different percentages of H_2SO_4 as catalyst as shown below.

TABLE V

Authors.	% H_2SO_4 used.	Types of acetates produced.
1. Miles	5.5 to 16.5	Chloroform-soluble primary acetate in the beginning. Acetone-soluble secondary acetate on hydrolysis with 50% acetic acid.
2. Dreyfus	10.0 to 15.0	Chloroform-soluble primary acetate in the beginning. Acetone-soluble secondary acetate on hydrolysis with water alone.
3. Yarsley	10.0 to 16.0	Acetone-soluble primary acetate. Acetone-soluble secondary acetate on hydrolysis with 50% acetic acid.
4. Goswami & Chondhury*	1.8 to 8.0	Chloroform-soluble primary acetate. Acetone-soluble secondary acetate on hydrolysis with 50% acetic acid.
5. Do.	15.0 to 18.4	Powdery acetylated product insoluble in chloroform and acetone.

* *J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ind. & News Ed.*, 1946, 9, 145.

But in a series of experiments, undertaken during the present investigations the author has found that the use of much higher percentage of H_2SO_4 than hitherto employed (16.6, 18.4 and 20.2%) produces no adverse effect on the progress of acetylation. On the contrary, the acetates produced show exactly the similar solubility and practically the same acetic acid content as those formed by the use of lower percentage of H_2SO_4 (Tables III and IV).

The process of hydrolysis *i.e.* the addition of either dilute acetic acid or water alone to bring about the degradation of primary acetate into secondary acetate to impart into the resultant product, the property of dispersion in acetone to a varying degree is well recognised and well established. Chemically speaking, hydrolysis brings down the acetic acid content of the primary acetate to a lower figure, making the acetate with lower acetic acid content fall in line within the range where the secondary acetate is soluble both in chloroform and acetone, soluble only in acetone and finally insoluble even in acetone, if the hydrolysis is allowed to have its course.

In almost all the known methods of preparation of secondary acetates, this process is followed universally. Even Yarsley (*loc. cit.*), who claimed to have prepared an acetone-soluble primary acetate, had adopted hydrolysis with 50% acetic acid solution to obtain secondary acetate soluble in acetone.

The present author has found that the addition of either dilute acetic acid or water during the period of hydrolysis is not an essential factor for conversion of the primary into secondary acetates. The lowering down of the acetic acid content takes place even without the addition of water, the only factor affecting the whole process being the longer period required by this unhydrolysed primary acetate than that required by the primary acetate hydrolysed with dilute acetic acid (65% used by the author, vide Table IV).

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